

THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF OUR COUNTRY

Bostonova Nilufar Abdusamatovna

Andijan Machine-Building institute,Uzbekistan.

nilufarbustanova48@gmail.com, phone: +998 91 610-39-49

Abstract:

The purpose. The rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship is the main link that ensures the sustainable growth of the economy of any country and is the priority of the economic reforms being implemented. In our republic, ensuring the stability of small business and private entrepreneurship and supporting it is defined as one of the main priorities of the country's socio-economic development.

Methods. Small business and private entrepreneurship, as a sector of the economy that quickly adapts to changes, is gaining importance in filling the domestic market with consumer goods, expanding new and modern types of services, and developing export potential. Wide implementation of the decisions made on supporting small business and private entrepreneurship.

Results. Today, small business and private entrepreneurship are considered an important link that provides employment for the population and are its main source of income. Great attention is being paid to paving the way, making full use of their existing opportunities, conducting business activities on the basis of high efficiency, initiative and organization.

Summary. Today, many people correctly understand and realize the importance of business and entrepreneurship, because their basis is not always to start a profitable business or make money, but to benefit oneself, one's family, and the whole society, and that is prioritized.

Key words: small business, entrepreneurship, gross domestic product, tax, trade, goods

1. Introduction:

At every step of our practical life, today we witness how small business and private entrepreneurship play a decisive and influential role in the development of our country, first of all, in building a decent life for our people and in the implementation of complex and responsible tasks ahead of us.

The potential of any country is determined by its economy. After we gained independence, the way to private ownership was opened for the formation and development of business and private entrepreneurship. This increasing efficiency is the demand of the times.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "...there is another important direction that requires serious and daily attention. This is the further development of private property and entrepreneurship and their effective protection" [1]. The economic basis of our society is based on the market economy. Small business and private entrepreneurship occupy an important place as the basis of the market economy. In order to ensure the rapid development of this field, it is an objective necessity to improve the legal framework. Because the sphere of small business and private entrepreneurship in ensuring stable social and economic growth in our country is incomparable.

2. Methods.

Support of small business and private entrepreneurship provides economic goals related to continuous development of the economy, improvement of economic relations, development of competition and filling of the consumer market.

In order to make small business and private entrepreneurship more stable in our country, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Additional measures to fundamentally improve the system of organizing work on the protection of private

property and strengthening the guarantees of the rights of owners, supporting entrepreneurial initiatives, as well as the Decree No. PF-5780 of August 13, 2019 on expanding the opportunities of business entities to use financial resources and production infrastructure and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Small business under the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and on the organization of the activity of the entrepreneurship development agency" decisions No. PQ-4417 of August 13, 2019 were adopted.

In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, the following is noted about small business and private entrepreneurship: "...small business and private entrepreneurship are the creation of the national economy, the formation of the class of middle owners, which is considered the basis of the social stability of the society and an important factor in creating a competitive environment and achieving sustainable economic growth" [2]

In recent years, small business and private entrepreneurship, as a fast-changing sector of the economy, is gaining importance in filling the domestic market with consumer goods, expanding new and modern types of services, and developing export potential. As a result of the widespread implementation of the decisions taken on the support of small business and private entrepreneurship, the reduction of inspection work, financial and time costs for doing business, the introduction of the registration notification system, the indicators of their foreign trade activity are also positive trends. State support of small business entities and producing import-substituting and export-oriented products make it possible to increase the contribution of small business in the volume of exports.

It is very important to liberalize business activity in solving issues related to the development of the economy of our country and the creation of new jobs. If we consider the case of Andijan region as an example, the share of small business in

the gross regional product was 69.9 billion sums in 2020 and 71.8 billion sums in 2021. That shows that it increased by 1.9 billion sums.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are defined as the priority direction of our country's economy. In the last five years, about 2,000 laws, decrees and decisions aimed at the development of this industry have been adopted.

Based on them, 114 licenses and permits were canceled, 33 types of activity were transferred to the notification procedure. Procedures for issuing permits have been simplified, and their terms have been shortened by an average of 2 times. Excessive checks, many restrictions on cash, foreign exchange and raw materials have been eliminated. As a result of such convenience and opportunities, new subjects have increased dramatically and are expanding the activities of those already working. In the last five years, the number of entrepreneurs has increased almost 3 times. Many businessmen have expanded their business across the country, created thousands of jobs, and become prestigious companies. A class of entrepreneurs with their own prestige and brand began to form in the domestic and foreign markets.

In this table, the number of economic subjects in Andijan region as of 2021

(together)

The number of business entities - **43,754**

Of which, small business entities - **38,057**

The number of small business entities per 1000 inhabitants - **13.8**

Business entities organizational and legal form

(together)

Naming	Total number
Joint-stock companies (JSC)	40
Limited liability companies (LLC)	29290
Joint ventures (JV)	264

Foreign enterprises (FE)	126
Private enterprises (PE)	5156
Family businesses (FB)	3116
Individual entrepreneurs (IE)	35925
Of other forms	5762

As can be seen from the table, the highest figure is 35925 individual entrepreneurs.

3. Results.

In such a rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country, first of all, the tax incentives set for this sector are considered to be of sufficient incentive importance. In particular, the reduction of the value-added tax rate from 20% to 15% in 2020 gave confidence that 10 trillion sums will remain at the disposal of 100,000 entrepreneurs. From 2023, this tax rate has been reduced from 15 percent to 12 percent. In 2022, the property tax rate for small business entities was reduced from 2% to 1.5%. From 2023, property and land taxes will be combined and a single real estate tax will be introduced. The role of small business and private entrepreneurship in foreign economic activity is gradually expanding. Its share in the export volume was 13.7 percent in 2010, and 27.2 percent in 2018. Due to the recent pandemic, this indicator will increase by 20.5 percent or 4634.5 million in 2020.

With the growth of small business and private entrepreneurship, the task of forming the middle-class owners, which is the backbone of the country, is solved. Therefore, it is necessary to implement and organize production based on consumer requirements and open a wide way for citizens to engage in entrepreneurship, which is based on high efficiency, initiative and organization.

As a result of fundamental reforms implemented to support entrepreneurs and improve the business environment, in the World Bank's "Doing Business - 2020" report, Uzbekistan rose 7 places and took 69th place, and is among the top 20 reformers in the world. For the first time, our country has risen to eighth place in the world in terms of the ease of opening a new enterprise. As a result of such opportunities, 91,000 new business entities were established in the last 10 months of this year, or 2 times more than in 2018. But it should be noted that there is still a lot of work to be done in the field of development.

4. Summary.

Today, many people correctly understand the importance of business and entrepreneurship, because their basis is not always to start a profitable business, in other words, to collect money, but to benefit oneself, one's family, and the whole society. A businessman is not a capitalist, as we used to think, as we were taught, he is an entrepreneur, a person who has a desire to succeed in his work. It does not matter if the businessman (entrepreneur) or someone else from his team (in collective business) ensures success, as long as the entrepreneurial work complies with the current legal rules and norms.

Deepening economic reforms, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is one of the main directions of economic reforms taking place in our republic. This entails the development of economic competition, the replenishment of the consumer market with goods and types of services, as well as the creation of a wide layer of private entrepreneurs. Taking into account these, the following issues should be solved in the Republic today: - to bring the broad population into market activities, eliminate the psychology of immortality, consumerism in them, arouse in the population the desire to actively engage in private entrepreneurship, small business activities; - to radically renew economic relations in agriculture, further develop the activities of farmers and farms, and

increase, providing additional jobs for people temporarily unemployed by creating small enterprises in the regions;-creating conditions for accelerating market relations and infrastructure in the region, developing economic competition; - building economic and social conditions that serve to more fully meet the growing demand and needs of the population of the Republic; - to dramatically increase the type and scale of services provided, to ensure the organization of banking, auditing, consulting and various intermediary activities at a high level based on the achievements of modern science and technology;-to increase the efficiency of enterprise management, to create conditions for ensuring their economic independence; - introduction of small enterprises capable of producing goods for export, filling the consumer market with goods, which can easily adapt the types and volumes of products produced in places according to market requirements. It is known that more than 65% of the working population of the Republic lives in villages. This shows that there are huge opportunities for the development of entrepreneurship in rural areas. Alternatively, surplus labour employed in agricultural production needs to be serviced, processed and redistributed to similar lines.

In particular, it is necessary to eliminate the shortcomings indicated in the "Doing Business - 2020" report, including creating facilities for land allocation, construction, and property registration. That is why, it is necessary to provide inter-departmental electronic information exchange on the issue of land to entrepreneurs through an online auction and property registration. Based on foreign experience, it is also important to establish a separate structure responsible for transferring the right to property independently of the state registry.

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